

Impact of Curriculum Development on Entrepreneurship and Innovation Skills among Undergraduate Students in Nigeria

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Abstract

Nigeria's curriculum has evolved to emphasize critical thinking, innovation, and entrepreneurship, vital for addressing unemployment and economic growth. However, graduates often struggle to find employment due to curriculum implementation issues and insufficient focus on innovation. This study employs a descriptive survey design to investigate the "Impact of Curriculum Development on Entrepreneurship and Innovation Skills among Undergraduate Students in Nigeria". The population of the study consisted of two hundred and fifty-eight (258) public and private universities within Nigeria. Employing a non-probability purposive sampling method, the researchers selected a sample of three hundred students (300) from both public and private universities representing all six geopolitical zones of Nigeria. Data is collected from 300 students across public and private universities using a Likert-scale questionnaire. The t-test is employed to analyze mean assessment scores, showing significant differences in both entrepreneurial mindset and innovative skills between public and private universities. The reliability coefficient was calculated as 0.84. The data collected were analyzed using mean scores and simple percentages to answer research questions to address the research inquiries, while t-tests were employed to assess the test hypotheses at a 0.05 significant level. The study recommended among other things that, to address these issues and promote economic growth, Nigerian universities should adopt a practical and forward-thinking curriculum, with a particular focus on integrating collaborative curriculum development involving stakeholders and more funding for entrepreneurship programs. It also highlights the importance of innovative teaching methods to prepare graduates for the modern economy.

Keywords: Curriculum development, Innovative teaching methods, Entrepreneurial mindset, Entrepreneurial innovative skills

Introduction

The quality, sustainability, and progress of an educational system within any nation hinge upon the nature of its curriculum. Irrespective of its type, structure, or form, the curriculum stands as a masterpiece and the core of the educational system. The effectiveness and practicality of a country's educational framework are equally dependent on its curriculum. It goes beyond being a planned activity to transmit societal values, norms, virtues, and attitudes to the next generation. Rather, it encompasses subjects and courses offered across elementary schools, secondary schools, and higher learning institutions. It serves as a blueprint, meticulously designed for high-quality, impactful learning experiences that are standardized and finely crafted by educational institutions or governmental bodies. This blueprint guides students mentally and developmentally in achieving societal goals while preparing them for the challenges of their environment. According to Ikelegbe and Odiachi (2017), the curriculum is a series of organized experiences in a logical sequence, designed to equip individuals for proficient performance in specific vocations.

Curriculum development involves the input of curriculum experts who significantly influence the scope and nature of curricular activities. This process should also involve teachers and students at every stage of designing the curriculum, spanning from planning and structuring to organization, implementation, and assessment. The goal is to achieve educational objectives that prepare students for life beyond schooling. Curriculum development is a continuous, dynamic, and progressive process aimed at maintaining the curriculum's relevance, adaptability, and responsiveness to societal needs. It remains open to revision or alteration according to society's evolving demands. Educational systems worldwide are built upon curricula, albeit with variations tailored to individual societal needs and purposes. The traditional Nigerian curriculum reflected past societal norms, beliefs, attitudes, values, knowledge, and skills passed down generations within a close-knit, communal community. While reading and writing weren't integral components of the traditional Nigerian curriculum, it was pragmatic and aligned with the community's needs. The present Nigerian curriculum, following multiple revisions post-Independence, is divided into Basic Education, known as Universal Basic Education (UBE), encompassing a mandatory 9-year continuous schooling period (6 years in primary school and 3 years in junior secondary school). This is followed by 3 years of senior secondary school and 4

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years of tertiary education, known as the 9-3-4 system. The modern Nigerian curriculum aims to instill value reorientation, critical thinking, innovative skills, entrepreneurship mindset, and lifelong skills among its youth to meet the demands of the technology-driven 21st century.

Nigerian policymakers and educators recognize the pivotal role of science and technology in achieving education for all and national development in the present era. Entrepreneurial mindset and innovation skills play a vital role in employment, critical thinking, creativity, decision-making, wealth creation, and economic prosperity. Thus, these attributes are now part of the Nigerian curriculum. Entrepreneurial mindset integrated into the curriculum aims to equip students with the necessary foundation to expand their entrepreneurial thinking from an early stage. This is to ensure they possess the requisite background and knowledge to embark on entrepreneurial ventures once they enter the workforce.

Entrepreneurship involves identifying, initiating, organizing, and realizing ideas or visions, whether they pertain to products, services, processes, strategies, or markets. In the current economic climate, there's a pressing need to cultivate students' general cognitive abilities over personal attributes. This is particularly important due to high unemployment rates and limited job opportunities. Developing entrepreneurial skills among university students entails fostering critical thinking, idea generation, and a commitment to entrepreneurial goals upon graduation. Innovation is the ability to introduce or use new ideas or methods. It involves thinking creatively, manipulating variables to create models, discovering possibilities, and forming objects and images that didn't exist before.

To achieve sustainable development, an entrepreneurial mindset, and innovative skills must be embedded within the curriculum. Nigeria's potential for creativity, human capital, and unique resources positions it well for economic growth and development. Therefore, the curriculum should encourage inventiveness, reflective thinking, rationality, creativity, innovation, and overall better output. This will contribute to fostering a culture of innovation and entrepreneurship, leading the nation toward a more sustainable and prosperous future. In Nigeria, despite the abundant human and material resources, the educational system, including higher institutions, grapples with unstable and inconsistent educational policies. These policies have led to tumultuous curriculum implementation. Over time, Nigerian educational institutions have been producing graduates lacking essential skills, such as self-reliance, employability, innovation, and an entrepreneurial mindset. This deficiency hampers the nation's progress, even in the face of available resources. This situation has dire consequences, including a dwindling economy, high unemployment rates, unsuitable economic policies for small and medium-scale businesses, inflation, and an inability to meet the technological demands of the 21st century.

A publication by the National Bureau of Statistics (2016) reveals that 52 million economically active citizens in Nigeria are unemployed, mainly comprised of recent university graduates. This situation is exacerbated by the fact that Nigeria boasts a youth population of 80 million, representing 60% of the total population. Within this demographic, 64 million youths are unemployed, while 1.6 million are underemployed. In the first quarter of this year, Nigeria's youth unemployment rate reached a staggering 53%, second only to South Africa's 61%. This escalating unemployment trend is alarming and presents a significant challenge to Nigeria's stability and growth. To address these challenges, a curriculum that instills an entrepreneurial mindset and innovation skills is essential. However, despite the incorporation of entrepreneurship education into the curriculum, the unemployment rate remains high. Inadequate curriculum implementation, the lack of focus on innovation skills, and insufficient funding hinder the development of an entrepreneurial mindset among students. Flexibility is vital to cater to student's needs and create an environment conducive to entrepreneurship education. The concept of entrepreneurship education aims to provide students with the knowledge and skills to cultivate entrepreneurial thinking from an early stage. Entrepreneurship involves identifying, initiating, and bringing ideas to fruition, while innovation entails introducing new ideas or methods. A robust curriculum should equip students with these skills, enabling them to be self-employed and contribute positively to the economy.

However, despite the incorporation of entrepreneurship education into the Nigerian curriculum, many graduates remain unemployable. Inadequate funding, underfunding by state governments, and low-quality teaching contribute to this challenge. To truly harness the potential of an entrepreneurial mindset and innovation skills, a functional and pragmatic curriculum is necessary. This curriculum should be developed collaboratively with input from teachers, professionals, curriculum experts, and successful entrepreneurs. Innovation in the curriculum should emphasize broad competence, integrative learning experiences, and innovative instructional methods. Other countries also recognize the importance of entrepreneurship education. For example, the United States' Bridging Disciplinary Program at the University of Texas combines courses from various fields to teach students how ideas, inventions, and skills are transformed into commercial ventures. To achieve similar success in Nigeria, the government should provide adequate funding for entrepreneurship programs, train teachers to promote creative and entrepreneurial skills and encourage practical and collaborative extracurricular activities. In conclusion, while

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Nigeria's curriculum incorporates entrepreneurship education, its implementation and effectiveness remain challenging due to poor funding and inadequate execution. A robust curriculum promoting an entrepreneurial mindset and innovation skills is crucial for Nigeria's economic growth and development. The collaboration of stakeholders, the provision of adequate funding, and innovative teaching methods are essential to ensuring graduates are equipped to thrive in the 21st-century economy.

Purpose of the study

The general objective of this study is to investigate the “Impact of Curriculum Development on Entrepreneurship and Innovative Skills among Undergraduate Students in Nigeria” The specific objectives were:

1. to ascertain the mean assessment scores of entrepreneurship education on students in promoting entrepreneurial mindset in public and private universities in Nigeria.
2. to determine the mean assessment scores of entrepreneurship education on students in promoting innovative skills in public and private universities in Nigeria.

Research Question

1. Is there a significant difference in the mean assessment scores of entrepreneurship education on students' promotion of entrepreneurial mindset between public and private universities in Nigeria?
2. Is there a significant difference in the mean assessment scores of entrepreneurship education on students' promotion of innovative skills between public and private universities in Nigeria?

Hypothesis

From the specific objectives of this study, the following null hypotheses were raised at 0.05 level of significance to guide the study.

H01: There is no significant difference in the mean assessment scores of entrepreneurship education on students in promoting entrepreneurial mindset in public and private universities in Nigeria.

H02: There is no significant difference in the mean assessment scores of entrepreneurship education on students in promoting innovative skills in public and private universities in Nigeria

Methodology

The researcher employed a descriptive survey research design to investigate the Impact of Curriculum Development on Entrepreneurship and Innovation Skills among undergraduate Students in Nigeria. The study's target population comprised two hundred and fifty-eight (258) public and private students within Nigeria. Employing a non-probability purposive sampling method, the researchers selected a sample of three hundred students (300) from both public and private universities representing all six geopolitical zones of Nigeria. Among these, two hundred students were selected from public universities (200), while one hundred students (100) were chosen from private universities. From each of the six universities, fifty students (50) were invited to participate in the study. The research had two objectives and corresponding hypotheses that guided the study and were tested at a significance level of 0.05. Data collection was facilitated through a questionnaire developed by the researcher, using a four-point Likert Scale that included Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD) options, rated as 4, 3, 2, and 1, respectively. The research instrument was validated by experts in test and measurement from the University of Abuja, ensuring alignment with the study's purpose and objectives; its reliability coefficient was calculated as 0.84. The data collected were analyzed using mean scores and simple percentages to answer the research questions, while t-tests were employed to test the hypotheses at 0.05 significant level.

Results

Hypothesis Testing

H01: There is no significant difference in the mean assessment scores of entrepreneurship education on students in promoting entrepreneurial mindset in public and private universities in Nigeria.

Table 1: T-test results on the difference in the mean assessment scores of entrepreneurship education on students in promoting entrepreneurial mindset in public and private universities in Nigeria.

Variables	N	X	SD	df	t-value	sig.(p)	Decision
Public University	200	2.61	0.101	298	-3.045	0.0029	Rejected
Private University	100	2.54	0.111				

*=significant at 0.05level (p<0.05)

Table 1 displays the statistical summaries and analysis of the mean assessment scores related to entrepreneurship education's impact on fostering an entrepreneurial mindset among students within both public and private universities in Nigeria. The computed mean for public universities stands at 2.61, accompanied by a standard deviation of 0.101. In comparison, the mean for private universities is calculated as 2.54, with a corresponding standard deviation of 0.111. The t-test conducted to assess the equality of means yields a p-value of 0.002, which falls below the 0.05 significance level. This outcome leads to the inference that a significant difference exists in the mean assessment scores for entrepreneurship education's influence on students' entrepreneurial mindset promotion between public and private universities in Nigeria.

H02: There is no significant difference in the mean assessment scores of entrepreneurship education on students in promoting innovative skills in public and private universities in Nigeria.

Table 2: T-Test Results on the Difference in the mean assessment scores of entrepreneurship education on students in promoting innovative skills in public and private universities in Nigeria

Variables	N	X	SD	df	t-value	sig.(p)	Decision
Public University	200	2.81	0.109	298	3.67	0.0000	Rejected
Private University	100	2.74	0.117				

*=significant at 0.05level (p<0.05)

Table 2 presents the statistical summaries and analysis concerning the mean assessment scores related to entrepreneurship education's influence on enhancing innovative skills among students in both public and private universities in Nigeria. The computed mean for public universities is established at 2.81, with a standard deviation of 0.109 and a standard error mean of 0.00465. In comparison, the mean for private universities is calculated as 2.78, with a corresponding standard deviation of 0.08160. The t-test conducted to evaluate the equality of means produces a p-value of 0.000, which falls below the 0.05 significance level. Consequently, this outcome leads to the deduction that a notable difference exists in the mean assessment scores for entrepreneurship education's impact on students' promotion of innovative skills between public and private universities in Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The findings illustrated in Table 1 unveil a substantial disparity in the mean assessment scores concerning entrepreneurship education's influence on fostering an entrepreneurial mindset among students in both public and private universities in Nigeria. These outcomes align with the insights gleaned from a study conducted by Ebringa, Ewenwa, and Ebringa (2015), which underscored the involvement of students in practical and collaborative entrepreneurial extracurricular activities, coupled with mentorship from seasoned entrepreneurial-minded academics. This approach equips students with critical thinking proficiencies conducive to entrepreneurial endeavours post-graduation. Further corroborating these findings is the research undertaken by Bodnar, Renee, and Mary (2015), which similarly demonstrated that the provisions within entrepreneurship curriculum content carry implications for cultivating entrepreneurship among university students, chiefly by inciting critical thinking capabilities and fostering competencies in generating business concepts.

Equally, the outcomes depicted in Table 2 unveil a marked variance in the mean assessment scores reflecting the impact of entrepreneurship education on enhancing innovative skills among students within both public and private universities in Nigeria. This alignment is consistent with the assertions posited by Mbanefo and Eboka (2017), who define innovativeness as the aptitude for introducing novel ideas or novel approaches to solving challenges. They further emphasize the innovation

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process, encompassing creative ideation, the imaginative manipulation of variables and instruments, the formulation of models, the exploration of potentials, and the creation of novel objects and images. This viewpoint resonates with the viewpoint of Mbanefo and Chiaha (2014), who contend that innovative learning environments prioritize the facilitation and application of novel modes of knowledge acquisition, the embrace of problem-solving strategies, the integration of diverse knowledge sources, the encouragement of self-directed learning, and the extension of knowledge through intricate creative expression.

Conclusion

The caliber, durability, and trajectory of advancement within the educational systems of all nations are intrinsically linked to the essence of their curriculum. Against the backdrop of Nigeria's considerable unemployment rate and the challenges faced by certain university graduates in securing employment, let alone creating jobs, a formidable obstacle emerges that hampers Nigeria's advancement in terms of economic growth and overall national progress. This situation underscores the pressing need for Nigerian universities to adopt a forward-looking approach in the context of our innovative era. The potential solution rests in the adoption of an educational curriculum that is not only practical but also pragmatic and hands-on. At the core of this endeavor lies the integration of entrepreneurship education, which serves as the cornerstone for cultivating an entrepreneurial mindset. This approach imparts vital attributes such as creativity, critical thinking, adept problem-solving skills, heightened productivity, and proficiency in innovation, among other competencies. Consequently, these attributes comprehensively prepare university students to confidently confront and adeptly overcome the imminent challenges posed by our continually evolving, technology-driven society. This aligns with the recommendations derived from the findings of this study.

Recommendation

In light of the outcomes obtained through this research, the ensuing recommendations are put forth:

1. University administrations in Nigeria should establish a conducive milieu within their institutions by equipping them with fundamental facilities and tools that foster a hands-on environment for entrepreneurship education. This will effectively cultivate an entrepreneurial mindset among students in both public and private universities throughout Nigeria.
2. The government should allocate sufficient resources to support entrepreneurship education initiatives in Nigerian universities. Additionally, initiatives for the ongoing training and professional development of lecturers should be incentivized. This step is pivotal in nurturing innovative skills among students in public and private universities across Nigeria.

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